

SUITABILITY OF POULTRY OFFAL MEAL AS A SUBSTITUTE FOR MUSTARD OIL CAKE IN PRACTICAL FEEDS FOR FINGERLING *CHANNA STRIATUS* (BLOCH)

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ABSTRACT

The suitability of poultry offal meal as a suitable substitute for mustard oil cake was carried out in *Channa striatus* during June 2015 to May 2016. In most of the aquaculture operations, feeds accounts for more than one-half of the variable operating cost. Therefore, knowledge on nutrition and practical feeding of fish is essential to successful aquaculture. The replacement of MOC by PM on protein to protein basis was found to be suitable up to 60% as evident by in significant differences ($P < 0.05$) among the LWG (237-235), FCR (1.42-1.44). PER (1.76-1.73), SGR (4.05-4.03) in fish fed diet DO, D1 and D2. The replacement of MOC with PM beyond this level in diet D3 resulted in a marked reduction in the growth parameters. Significantly ($P > 0.05$) poor FCR, PER and SGR were observed in fish fed diet replacing MOC with PM beyond 60%. There are no significant difference in ($P < 0.05$) in moisture content were evident in fish fed diet DO, D1 and D2 but it significantly increased in diet D3 replacing 100% MOC with PM. The body protein remained almost unchanged in fish fed feed diet DO, D1 and D2 whereas in D3 showed significant ($P < 0.05$) declined in body protein content. The body fat content declined significantly ($P < 0.05$) at 100% replacement level of MOC with PM. Insignificant differences ($P > 0.05$) in body ash content were evident in fish fed diets DO, D1 and D2 but it significantly increased in fish fed diet D3.

Keywords: Poultry offal meal, Mustard oil cake, Fingerlings, *Channa striatus*.

INTRODUCTION

Aquaculture appears to have the potential to make the significant contribution to the increasing demand for aquatic food in all region of the world. The United Nation reports that nearly half of the world's total food fish supply comes from the aquaculture. With the emergence of aquaculture as a prime food-producing sector, the push towards higher yields and faster growth has evolved the enhancement or replacement of natural foods with prepared diets. In most of the aquaculture operations, feeds accounts for more than one-half of the variable operating cost. Therefore, knowledge on nutrition and practical feeding of fish is essential to successful aquaculture. Nutritional and feeding strategies play a central and essential role in the sustainable development of the aquaculture sector. As in other forms of animal husbandry, feeds and feeding crucial elements in the culture of aquatic animals (De Silva and Anderson, 1995). The aqua feed formulation also has been targeted and revised, to allow more appropriate transition from natural living to captivity and to improve the marketable yields.

Fish is highly nutritive and rich source of animal proteins. For the improvement of fisheries and to achieve

maximum yields from resources of freshwater, it is necessary to provide artificial feeds for maximizing the growth in shortest possible time. As other animals, fish requires a nutritious diet for proper growth and quality protein production. Since feed is one of the highest cost expenditure of an aquaculture entrepreneur often ranging from 30% to 60%, depending on the intensity of the operation (Akiyama and Chwang, 1989; Piedecausa *et al.*, 2007), any reduction in the feed cost is there for crucial to the development and well-being of the industry.

Mustard oil cake (MOC) is being frequently used as a protein source in the fish feed industry. MOC contain the high level of toxic substances i.e. glucosinolate, erucic acid, sinapine, tannin and some anti-nutrient factors (Roza *et al.*, 1996). These substances induce unpalatability, growth retardation, enlargement of thyroid gland, low feed efficiency and reproductive problems, particularly when the seed is incorporated into the diet at the high level. The Poultry offal meal one of the less economically rendered animal protein sources. It is a byproduct obtained from poultry processing industries that have high protein, balanced amino acid profile and better growth promotion effect compared to other feed ingredients. Poultry meal is

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readily available and is currently used in the pet industries. Some studies showed that poultry meal could partially replace dietary fishmeal without affecting growth and feed efficiency of experimental fish (Davies *et al.*, 1991; El-Sayed, 1998; Bureau *et al.*, 2000).

Channa striatus or Murrels or Snakehead fish occupy the top rank among commercially important fresh water fish species due to their taste, fewer intramuscular spines and medicinal qualities. These fishes are air-breathers, survive oxygen depleted water bodies and hence are suitable for profitable culture in shallow systems *C. striatus* and marshes. Its food mainly consists of crustaceans, mollusks, insects, fishes, plants and semi-digested materials. The juveniles and adult *C. striatus* are surface feeder. The present study was, therefore, undertaken to ascertain whether poultry meal (PM) could replace a significant portion of Mustard oil cake (MOC) in practical diets for the carnivorous fish *C. striatus*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Preparation of experimental diets

Fish meal (FM), soybean meal (SM), mustard oil cake (MOC), poultry meal and wheat bran (WB) were used as the dietary ingredients. FM was prepared by drying and powdering low-quality fish (Alexis *et al.*, 1985). The resulting FM is low-quality as it contained high levels of ash (Table.1). Based on the nutrient composition of the ingredients, four isonitrogenous (40% CP) and isoenergetic (15.05 KJ/g GE) diets were prepared by replacing 30% (D1), 60% (D2) and 100% (D3) MOC with PM (Table 1). A control diet (D0) with the same level of CP and GE which excluded the contribution of poultry meal as a protein source was also prepared. All the ingredients were weighed and blended in a Hobart electric mixer thoroughly and mixed with vitamin, mineral and oil premixes in a Hobart electrical mixer (Model 120A, Troy USA). These were then steam cooked at 80°C in a volume of hot water. Water was added gradually until the desirable paste-like consistency was reached. The final diet was packed in polythene bags and kept in a freezer at -4°C till further uses (Bureau *et al.*, 2000).

Experimental design and feeding trial

C. striatus was obtained from local water bodies. These were transported to the wet laboratory, given a prophylactic dip in KMNO₄ solution (1:3000) and stocked in indoor circular aqua-blue coloured, plastic lined (Plastic corp, Mumbai, India, 122 m X 0.91m X 0.91M) fish tanks (water volume 600L) for a fortnight. During this period, the fish were fed to apparent satiation a mixture of mustard oil cake, rice bran and wheat middling in the form of crumbles twice a day at 09:00 and 16:30 hour. For conducting the experiment, fingerlings (9.0±0.15 g; 9.2±0.18 cm) were sorted out from the acclimated lot and stocked in triplicate groups in 70 L circular polyvinyl troughs (water volume 55 L) fitted with a continuous water flow through (1-1.5 L/min) system at the rate of 7 fish per trough for each

dietary treatment (Davies *et al.*, 1991). Fish were fed test diets in the form of crumbles to apparent satiation twice daily at 09:00 and 16:30 hour. No feed was offered to the fish on the day they were weighed. Initial and weekly weights were recorded on a top loading balance (Precisa 120A; 0.1 mg sensitivity, Oerlikon, AG, Zurich, Switzerland). The feeding trial lasted for 5 weeks. Faecal matter and unconsumed feed, if any, were siphoned off. The unconsumed feed was collected soon after active feeding, dried and weighed to measure the amount of feed consumed.

Proximate analysis

Assessment of proximate composition of ingredients, diets and carcass were made using a standard technique (AOAC, 1995). All the analyses were done on the triplicate basis.

Moisture

A known quantity of sample was taken in the pre-weighed crucible and placed in a hot air oven at 105±1°C for 24 hours. After complete drying, the sample was cooled at room temperature in desiccators and was reweighed. The loss in weight gave an index of water from which its percentage was calculated.

Ash

A known quantity of dried powdered sample (2-5 g) was taken in a pre-weighed silica crucible and incinerated in a muffle furnace (600°C) for 2-4 hours or till the sample became carbon-free and completely white. The crucible was cooled in desiccators and reweighed to estimate the quantity of ash. The result was expressed as the percentage on dry weight basis.

Crude fat

The crude fat was estimated by continuous soxhlet extraction technique (Socs plus, Socs 4, pelican equipment, Chennai, India) using petroleum ether (40-60°C B.P.) as the solvent. Finely powdered and dried sample (2-4 g) was placed in fat extraction thimble and placed in the soxhlet apparatus. A clean, dry soxhlet receiver flask was weighed and fitted to the soxhlet assembly on a boiling water bath for extraction (De Silva and Anderson, 1995). After extraction, the flask was removed and kept in hot air oven (100°C) to evaporate the traces of solvent. It was then transferred to desiccators, cooled and weighed. The difference between the flask before and after gave the quantity of crude fat extracted from the unknown amount of the sample (Pokomy, 1982). The result was expressed as the percentage on dry weight basis.

Crude protein

The crude protein was estimated by a slight modification of Wrong's Micro-Kjeldhal method. 100 mg of the dry powdered sample was treated with 5 ml diluted (1:1) sulphuric acid in Kjeldhal flask and boiled for a few minutes till fumes disappeared. After cooling, 5 ml standard

potassium per sulphate solution was added to oxidize the digesting mixture. The digestion was continued till the solution in the Kjeldhal flask became water clear, indicating that all the nitrogenous material present in the sample has been converted into ammonium sulphate. The solution was diluted to 50 ml with distilled water. 0.5 ml aliquot of the digested sample was mixed with 0.1 ml of each dilute (1:1) sulphuric acid and saturated potassium per sulphate. The content was raised to 3 ml with distilled water. This was then nesslerized with 7 ml nessler's reagent. The solution was kept at room temperature for 10 minute for complete colour development. A blank was prepared, side by side substituting the aliquot with distilled water. The colour was read on a spectrophotometer at 480 nm. The intensity of colour developed was promotional to the amount of ammonium sulphate contained in the solution. The values of optical density obtained for various samples was read off against a standard calibration curved prepared by taking the reading of series of different dilutions containing different grades of known amount of nitrogen in the stock solution. The crude protein was calculated by multiplying the nitrogen value with protein factor (6.25). The values recorded as the percentage on dry weight basis (El-Sayed, 1998).

Gross energy

The gross energy was estimated by a bomb calorimeter (Gallenkamp, Loughbrough, England). Prior to estimate, a known quantity of dried powdered sample (0.5-1.0 g) was taken in metallic crucible and compacted carefully to increase the rate of combustion at 25 lb oxygen pressure. The heat generated upon combustion was read on the modulated galvanometer scale, and converted to energy equivalent, and worked out earlier using the thermo chemical grade benzoic acid (26.42 KJ/g) as a standard. The energy of ingredients used in the test diet was 15.05, 16.3, 14.63, 17.13, 12.96 and 37.62 KJ/g for fish meal and oil, respectively, which was estimated on a Gallenkamp ballistic bomb calorimeter (FAO, 2006).

Data collection and statistical analysis

The growth performance and nutrient utilization indices measured were live weight gain (LWG %), specific growth rate (SGR %), feed conversion ratio (FCR), feed intake (FI), protein efficiency ratio (PER), survival rate (SR %), hepatosomatic index (HIS %), viscera somatic index (VSI %) and condition factor (CF). These indices were calculated as: live weight gain % = final body weight – initial body weight / initial body weight x 100; SGR (%) = (In final body weight) – (In initial body weight) / Number of days x 100; FCR = Dry feed fed (g) / final body weight; PER = Wet weight gain (g) / Protein intake (g); SR (%) = (Fnal fish number / Initial fish number) x 100; HIS (%) = Liver weight (g) / Body weight (g) x 100; VSI (%) = Visceral weight (g) / Body weight (g) x 100; CF (K) = Body weight (g) /L³ (g) x 100 (Association of official Analytical Chemists, 1995).

Comparison among different dietary treatments was made using one-way analysis of variance as described by (Sokal and Rohlf, 1981). Differences among treatment means were determined by Duncan's Multiple Range Test at a P<0.05 level of significance. The software used for all mathematical operations was SPSS, version (13.0). Values throughout the text are expressed as means ±standard error of three replicates (n=3).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the present study, replacement of MOC by PM on protein to protein basis was found to be suitable up to 60% as evident by in significant differences (P<0.05) among the LWG (237-235), FCR(1.42-1.44). PER (1.76-1.73), SGR (4.05-4.03) in fish fed diet DO, D1 and D2 (Table.2). However, further replacement of MOC with PM beyond this level in diet D3 resulted in a marked reduction in the growth parameters. Significantly (P>0.05) poor FCR, PER and SGR were observed in fish fed diet replacing MOC with PM beyond 60% (Nengas *et al.*, 1999).

Body composition data of the fish fed different diets are given in (Table 3). No significant difference in (P<0.05) in moisture content were evident in fish fed diet DO, D1 and D2. However, it significantly increased in diet D3 replacing 100% MOC with PM. Body protein remained almost unchanged in fish fed feed diet DO, D1 and D2 whereas fish fed diet D3 showed significant (P<0.05) declined in body protein content. The body fat content declined significantly (P<0.05) at 100% replacement level of MOC with PM. In significant differences (P>0.05) in body ash content were evident in fish fed diets DO, D1 and D2. However, it significantly increased in fish fed diet D3.

HIS, VSI and CF was significantly (P<0.05) influenced by the levels of replacement of MOC with PM. These parameters remained unaffected up to a replacement level of 60% (D2) beyond which significant changes were noted (Piedecausa *et al.*, 2007).

In the present study, replacement of MOC by PM on protein to protein basis was found to be suitable up to 60% as evident by in significant differences. However, further replacement of MOC with PM beyond this level in diet D3 resulted in a marked reduction in the growth parameters. Body composition data of the fish fed different diets are given in (Table 3). No significant difference in (P<0.05) in moisture content were evident in fish fed diet DO, D1 and D2. However, it significantly increased in diet D3 replacing 100% MOC with PM. Body protein remained almost unchanged in fish fed feed diet DO, D1 and D2 whereas fish fed diet D3 showed significant (P<0.05) declined in body protein content. The body fat content declined significantly (P<0.05) at 100% replacement level of MOC with PM. In significant differences (P>0.05) in body ash content were evident in fish fed diets DO, D1 and D2 however, it significantly increased in fish fed diet D3.

Table 1. Ingredients and proximate composition of the experimental diet.

Ingredients	0%	30%	60%	100%
(g 100g ⁻¹ dry diet)	D0	D1	D2	D3
Fish meal	21.7	21.7	21.7	21.7
Soybean meal	26.50	26.5	26.5	26.5
Mustard oil cake	26.31	18.42	10.52	0
Wheat bran	14.20	14.20	14.20	14.20
Poultry meal	0	9.09	18.18	30.30
Cod liver oil	1	1	1	1
Soybean oil	2	2	2	2
Mineral mix	1	1	1	1
Vitamin mix	1	1	1	1
Carboxymethyl cellulose	1	1	1	1
Alpha-cellulose	4.29	3.09	1.90	0.30
Total	100	100	100	100
Analyzed crude protein	39.8	39.4	39.7	40.5
Gross energy (kJg ⁻¹)	15.05	15.05	15.05	15.05

Table 2. Growth and conversion efficiencies of fingerling *Channa striatus* fed diets replacing mustard oil cake with poultry meal.

Growth Parameters	D0	D1	D2	D3
Average initial weight (g) ¹	9.05±0.02	9.18±0.01	9.09±0.02	9.04±0.02
Average final weight (g) ¹	30.5±0.61	30.8±0.25	30.5±0.70	20±0.30
Live weight gain (%)	237±11	235±5	235±8	121±8
Feed conversion ratio	1.42±0.02	1.43±0.02	1.44±0.03	2.98±0.04
Protein efficiency ratio	1.76±0.01	1.75±0.01	1.73±0.03	0.84±0.02
Specific growth rate (%)	4.05±0.05	4.03±0.07	4.03±0.01	2.65±0.04
Feed intake	30.46±0.13	30.91±0.55	30.83±0.14	33±0.15

Mean values of 3 replicates ± SE.

Table 3. Body composition of fingerling *Channa striatus* fed replacing mustard oil cake with slaughter house waste.

Body composition	Initial	0%	30%	60%	100%
Moisture	78.6±0.30	77.9±0.03	78.9±0.06	78.7±0.011	79.1±0.05
Protein	13.9±0.34	16.8±0.11	16.4±0.3	16.3±0.10	14.5±0.10
Fat	3.1±0.25	3.8±0.01	3.7±0.03	3.9±0.02	3.1±0.09
Ash	2.5±0.14	2.3±0.01	2.5±0.03	2.4±0.13	3.1±0.19

Mean values of 3 replicates ± SE.

Table 4. Somatic indices of fingerling *Channa striatus* fed replacing mustard oil cake with slaughter house waste.

	Hepatosomatic index (HSI %)	Viscerosomatic index (VSI %)	Condition factor (CF)
D0	1.16±0.41	1.83±0.41	1.19±0.51
D1	1.17±0.34	1.84±0.41	1.18±0.14
D2	1.17±0.25	1.85±0.41	1.19±0.21
D3	1.97±0.14	1.97±0.41	1.01±0.13

Mean values of 3 replicates±SEM; (n=6x3) mean values sharing the same super scripts in a row are insignificantly different (P>0.05).

HIS, VSI and CF was significantly ($P < 0.05$) influenced by the levels of replacement of MOC with PM. These parameters remained unaffected up to a replacement level of 60% (D2) beyond which significant changes were noted.

The present study reveals that PM can replace up to 60% of MOC in the diet for soli without hampering growth and feed utilization efficiency. Poultry meal (PM) is completely suitable as a partial or complete replacement in a diet for rainbow trout, *Oncorhynchus mykiss* (Steffens, 1994); however, complete substitution required amino acid supplementation, principally lysine and methionine. Similarly Alexis *et al.* (1985) reported a diet containing 25% PM obtained satisfactory performance data in trout. Pokorny (1982) reported that diets including up to 40% PM and 10% poultry fat could successfully be used as a substitute for FM in trout. PM is high in ether extract, ash and indigestible components (feathers, etc.), resulting in reduced digestibility (Robinson and Li, 1999). However, if suitable raw ingredient is chosen and properly processed, a high-quality protein feed can be achieved.

FCR data of the present study suggested that 60% mustard oil cake can be replaced by poultry meal in diets for *C. striatus*. Further, these results are similar to those reported by Webster *et al.* (2000) and Lee *et al.* (2002). The lower growth rate at higher replacement level may be attributed to imbalanced amino acid profile and the poor digestibility induced by higher ash content present in PM.

HIS, VSI and CF data in this study also indicated no significant differences among the treatments up to the replacement of 60% MOC with PM. Further replacement of MOC with resulted in increased HIS, VSI and poor CF. These findings are in accordance with the findings of Zoccarato *et al.* (1996) who reported that high PM levels could cause increased HIS and VSI and also poor CF. This study indicated that 60% MOC could be replaced by PM in diets for *C. striatus* without any significant impairment of growth.

Crude protein fish meal (69%), soybean meal (49%), mustard oil cake (35%), wheat bran (14%), poultry meal (33%), mineral mixture and vitamin mixture (1 g vitamin mix +2 g α -cellulose) calculated on the basis of physiological fuel values 15.05, 16.3, 14.63, 17.13, 12.96 and 37.67 kJg⁻¹ for fish meal, soybean meal, wheat bran, mustard oil cake, poultry meal and fat respectively.

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